

Features Of The Development Of The Process Of Urbanization In The Republic Of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the development of the network of urban settlements of the Republic of Uzbekistan over the years of Independence. The growth of cities in the republic is described. Conclusions are given on the change in the urban settlement of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords — urbanization, urban population, territorial-urban structure, functional typology of cities, classification of cities, settlement system.

INTRODUCTION.

In the modern era, there is a growing interest in studying the growth of cities and the transformation of urban settlement into conditions of market relations. Urbanization process growth of cities and formation of urban settlement systems is the result of socio-historical development each country. Analysis of the development of a network of urban settlements Uzbekistan over the years of independence testifies to changes in the number of cities, the share of urban population, functional typology of cities and their classification by size. One of the famous geo-urbanists G.M. Lappo about the emergence of urban settlements wrote: "Consideration this process and its results are essential for knowledge progress in the formation of state territory, development its land and other resources, identifying trends and features (including regional) of urban development in different historical situations" In geourbanism, an important point is the formal aspect of the town formation process, that is, legislatively fixed legal requirements urban status of a settlement As a result changes in the legislative basis for town formation in The Republic of Uzbekistan is undergoing significant changes among cities, urban-type settlements and, accordingly, in the country's urban population. Occurring socio-economic changes, manifestations of new patterns of development and placement of productive forces, transformation of sectoral and territorial production structure is reflected in the growth of cities and formation of an urban settlement network. At the same time, special Of interest is the classification of cities by size and functional profile. As of January 1, 2023, in More than 36.0 million people live in Uzbekistan, of which 18.3 million people (50.9%) are urban, and 17.7 million people. (49.1%) – rural residents.

In the republic, according to 1991 data, there were 123 cities and 104 urban villages, total number whose population was 8366 thousand people, or 40.5% of the total population of the republic [3]. After the famous Resolutions of the Cabinet

of Ministers on some mitigation main criteria for town formation (2009) in the republic

the number of urban settlements has increased sharply, namely urban-type settlements. In 2009, the number of cities in there were 119 in the republic, and 1085 urban-type settlements,

At the same time, 51.7% of the total population of the republic lived in them. This happened due to the transfer of 966 rural settlements places to the rank of urban-type settlements. As a result of this reforms, the level of urbanization in the republic immediately increased from 35.8% to 51.7%. As of January 1, 2022

As of January 1, 2022, there were 1,182 urban settlements, 918, or more than 77% of which are urban settlements with a population of no more than 10 thousand people (Table 1).

Table 1

Territorial and urban structure of the Republic Uzbekistan (as of 01/01/2022)

Regions	Population, thousand people	Urban population, th	Number of urban settlements	
			Cities	
The Republic of Uzbekistan				
Republic of Karakalpakstan				

Note. The table was compiled by the authors based on materials from the official website of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/demography-2>

As evidenced by the data in Table 1, the urban population is especially high in the amangan, Fergana and Andijan regions. Here it is even higher than in the industrialized Tashkent region. It should be noted that, despite the agricultural specialization of the economy of the Namangan region, it has the highest level of urbanization - 64.8%. This situation is associated with the artificial transfer to the rank of urban settlements in the regions of the Fergana Valley of a significant number of rural settlements that do not meet the qualitative criteria for the status of urban settlements.

Changes in the main criteria for urban development in the republic directly affected the classification of cities by population (Table 2).

Table 2

Grouping of cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan by number of inhabitants (as of January 1, 2022)

From 500 thousand to 1 million people.		
From 250 thousand to 500 thousand people.		Andijan, Nukus, Fergana, Karshi, Bukhara
From 100 thousand to 250 thousand people.		Angren, Almalyk, Termez, Chirchik, Kokand, Margilan,

		Navoi, Urgench, Shakhrisabz, Jizzakh
From 50 thousand to 100 thousand people.		Asaka, Beruni, Gulistan, Denau, Kattakurgan, Zarafshan, Kasan, Kasansay, Kuvasay, Kuva, Kagan, Khojeyli, Turtkul, Takhiatash, Chimbay, Chust, Chartak, Shahrikhan, Yangiyul, Urgut, Khiva, Bekabad, Nurafshon, Parkent
From 20 thousand to 50 thousand people.		Kitab, Mubarek, Chirakchi, Uchkuduk, Pap, Turakurgan, Mangit, Gallyaaral, Nurata, Uchkurgan, Kungrad, Khanabad, Jalakuduk, Paytug, Kurgantepa, Karasu, Pakhtaabad, Khojaabad, Gijduvan, Karakul, Dashtobod, Dustlik, Pakhtakor, Guzar, Kamashi, Beshkent, Yakkabag, Hakkulabad, Bulungur, Aktash, Chelek, Jambay, Juma, Baysun, Dzharkurgan, Sherabad, Shurchi, Yangier, Syrdarya, Akhangaran, Gazalkent, Buka, Keles, Pskent, Chinaz, Besharyk, Rishtan, Yaipan
Up to 20 thousand people		Khalkabad, Muynak, Shumanai, Bustan, Markhamat, Alat, Galaasiya, Vabkent, Romitan, Gazli, Karaulbazar, Shafirkan, Gagarin, Yangi Nishan, Talimarjan, Kyzyltepa, Yangirabat, Gazgan, Ishtykhan, Nurabad, Payaryk, Kumkurgan, Shargun, Shirin, Bakht, Yangiabad, Akkurgan, Dustabad, Tinchlik, Pitnak

Note. The table was compiled by the authors based on materials from the official website of the State Committee of the Republic

Uzbekistan according to statistics <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/demography-2>

An analysis of the grouping of cities by population shows that although in general the number of cities in the period 1991-2022. remains practically at the same level, significant shifts are observed in the hierarchical structure of the network of cities in terms of their population.

Structural and institutional transformations in the economy, the slow development of city-forming industries directly affected the formation of cities in the republic and its urbanization. In 2022, there were 120 cities on the territory of Uzbekistan, including 1 millionaire city, 2 cities with a population of 500 thousand to 1 million people, 5 cities with a population of 250,500 thousand people, 10 cities with a population of 100 to 250 thousand people, 24 cities with a population of 50-100 thousand people. and 78 cities, or 65% of the total number of cities in the republic, with a population of up to 50 thousand people.

Towns and cities occupy a small share in the country's urban settlement system. Only 18 cities with a population of more than 100 thousand people make up this group. These cities are distinguished by a number of demographic, social, and urban planning features, being an indicator of the socio-economic development and level of urbanization of the country

An analysis of the study of trends in the development of urban settlement and the process of urbanization in the Republic of Uzbekistan allowed us to draw the following conclusions:

- the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in 2009 on some softening of the main criteria for urban development led to a rapid increase in the number of urban settlements and the size of the urban population, but many former rural settlements converted into urban settlements do not meet the requirements of urban settlements in terms of quality indicators;

- during the years of Independence, in conditions of market relations, there were no significant changes in the number of cities and the formation of urban systems; weak progress was also noted in the functional development and structure of cities by population;

- one of the main problems of urban development and the formation of urban systems in Uzbekistan is the development of production potential, social development and rational use of the economic potential of the regions;

- in recent years, the city of Tashkent has been growing in the republic, associated with the expansion of its territory and borders, as well as intensive migration of the population from other regions of the republic.

References

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